

Review and Propose a Research Model for Foreign Tourism Intentions

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Abstract:

This research aims to find an intrinsic law of the relationship between the factors affecting the customer behavior. Specifically, the act of making decisions to travel abroad of Vietnamese people. To achieve that goal, the author has established a theoretical model of the relationship between the factors and tested that model with actual collected data. The results obtained from the research have theoretical implications, enriching understanding of the relationship between factors in the context of specific research in Vietnam. In addition, this research result is also a valuable reference source for businesses in business activities, helping policy managers better understand the mechanism of the foreign tourism market.

Keywords: Literature review, Intention, foreign tourism

1. Introduction

Research on consumer behavior plays an important role and is the focus of research in many sciences such as psychology, sociology, economics and especially marketing. All studies try to understand and explain the mechanisms of consumer behavior. From personal psychological characteristics to the influences of the external social environment are deeply concerned by researchers. Research on consumer behavior involves all aspects of buying behavior - from pre-purchase activities to consumer activities, post-purchase reviews and feelings. In particular, the focus of behavioral research is on efforts to further elucidate how consumers make decisions, which are considered very unpredictable.

In behavioral economics and marketing, consumer decision-making research has long received much attention from organizations and researchers for its importance in economic development. The choice and decision to use products and services is not only important to consumers but also has great implications for marketers, regulators and policy makers. Researching consumer buying decision-making is important to marketing in the tourism sector. Isaac asserted that "customer behavior research is the key underpinning all marketing activities that help develop, promote and sell travel products" (Isaac, 2008, p. 74). From the business perspective, it is meaningful to understand the nature of the impact factors, determine who is the buyer and who are the customer selection criteria for products and services. important. It helps businesses know where to impact in order to effectively exploit their target market. Studies of many authors confirm the factors influencing consumer decision-making behaviors (Erasmus et al., 2001; Kardes et al., 2011; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004), and especially Tourist decisions (Decrop, 2006b; Moital, 2006; Luo and Zhong, 2015) always change according to different research contexts. Theories about the impact of factors also require constant updating to ensure the comprehensiveness of theoretical models applied in the periods. In the current period, along with the explosion of science and technology and the global internet, a number of basic factors affecting the consumption decisions of tourists compared to the studies before 2000. The rapid emergence and popularity of social media and internet media is changing both the intensity and the way factors influence consumer decisions.

This is especially fast for the travel business, which is widely regarded as relying heavily on information technology and internet communications. With the change in the social and scientific and technological contexts as above, the theoretical requirement is that the need for updated studies to deepen the understanding of consumer behavior, especially consumption used by tourists.

Not only research on domestic destination selection, but research on factors influencing foreign tourist destination selection reflects a more comprehensive and comprehensive picture of the tourism market. Thanks to a better understanding of the factors that influence a customer's decision to choose an overseas travel

destination, businesses, destination managers and policy makers can adjust their strategies to ensure that Make full use of competitive advantages.

Although there have been many studies on the factors that influence the decision to travel around the world and Vietnam. Most studies are based on the theoretical basis of the decision to choose a tourist destination. However, foreign tourist destinations have their own characteristics such as different tourist environment (socio-cultural environment, language, natural landscape and climate ...); differences in design of tourism programs (different from domestic tourism programs); Immigration, language barriers ... These particular characteristics can affect the tourists' decisions that need to be made clear. Meanwhile, theories related to outbound travel are carefully researched in the developed societies and Western cultures. Not much research has provided theories to explain the booming trend of overseas tourism in Eastern cultures (Lee et al., 2012). The case of Vietnam is no exception. In particular, it is very rare that studies in a general way that test the theories of foreign travel decision-making have been introduced in and experimented in Western cultures into the cultural environment practical socialization in Vietnam.

In practical terms, the growth of the overseas tour market for Vietnamese in recent years has shown a rapidly increasing trend, the range of destinations for foreign tours is also expanding. all over the world. The report by Choong and Wong (2017) of MasterCard International Credit Organization shows that the total number of Vietnamese traveling abroad in 2016 reached 4.8 million and is forecasted to reach 7.5 million by 2021. , with Asia's second highest growth rate with estimated growth of 9.5% per annum. The growth rate of the number of Vietnamese tourists to some foreign tourist markets such as Thailand, Malaysia, Japan, South Korea ... was always high in the period from 2010 to 2019. Report from The survey by Visa International Credit Organization (2018) shows that the average payout of Vietnamese people for each foreign tour in 2018 is US \$ 880 and it is forecasted that this figure will increase to 1100 USD. US dollar by 2021. The current situation of the foreign tourism market in Vietnam poses many challenges for businesses and policy managers. Although there have been a number of recent domestic studies mentioning the influence of these factors on travel decisions, the only explanation in the research context is the Vietnamese people's travel choice. go in the water. In fact, there is a huge difference between domestic and foreign tours in terms of consumer demand, tourism product design characteristics, destination attractiveness, barriers to customs, language ... etc. With this difference, research enriching understanding of the factors affecting the decision of Vietnamese to travel abroad is essential. It is not only important for business development activities of travel businesses but also plays an important role in building regulatory mechanisms for policy makers. This is the basis for the state management agency in charge of tourism to adjust the balance between the arrivals and arrivals market in a reasonable way.

2. Literature review

2.1. Concepts of consumer behavior and travel decision making

Up to now, consumer behavior is still the topic attracting a lot of research attention around the world. Not only economics, psychology or sociology, but other sciences such as management science and marketing also spend a lot of research topics on consumer behavior. Therefore, the concept of consumer behavior of goods and services has been mentioned in many studies over many decades.

Yadin (2002, p. 86) argues that "in a marketing environment, consumer behavior is the result of observing decision-making patterns, buying behavior and public habits. Behavioral science is heavily developed in the research of marketing, in the sense that consumer behavior can be analyzed and predicted. Group consumer behavior can be more predictable than individual behavior".

Some other authors define consumer behavior as "the activities consumers perform in the possession, consumption and disposition of products and services" (Blackwell et al., 2001) or the concept of behavior. Consumption is defined by Hoyer and MacInnis (2008, p. 3) "consumer behavior that reflects all consumer

decisions about the purchase, consumption and disposition of goods, services and activities. experiences, and ideas of a decision maker”.

According to Kapoor and Madichie (2012, p. 3), consumer behavior is' defined consumer behavior that explains how consumers make decisions about spending with their limited resources, eg time, effort and money to buy goods”. At the same time, customer behavior studies also try to explain "what consumers choose to get out of this product or service and what they have declined for another product or service".

Extending from the above concepts, Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2010, p. 6) argue that “The connotation of consumer behavior is the study of individuals, groups or organizations and the processes they use. to select, secure, use and dispose of products, services, experiences or ideas to meet the needs and impacts that these processes have on consumers and society”

Kotler (2017) argues that consumers make a lot of buying decisions every day and that buying decisions are at the heart of marketers. Most of the research has focused on detailed consumer buying decisions to answer questions about what consumers buy, where, how and how much, and when. buy and why do they buy. But learning about the problems behind consumer buying behavior isn't so easy, answers are often locked deep in the consumer's mind. Usually, consumers themselves don't know exactly what influences their purchase, according to Kotler (2017). The central question for marketers is: How do consumers react to the different marketing efforts that businesses may use?

The starting point is the stimulus - feedback model of buyer behavior shown in Kotler (2017) model which shows that marketing and other factors stimulate consumers' "black box of consciousness" and generate certain feedback about that product or service. To be able to understand how stimuli are transformed into the responses within the consumer black box needs to be based on two aspects: First, the characteristics of the buyer affect how they feel and react. with stimulation. These traits encompass a wide range of cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Second, it is a buyer's decision-making process that influences his or her behavior. This decision is the result of demand recognition, information retrieval, and assessment of alternative service products to purchasing and post-purchase decisions.

Developing from previous theories, some authors have proposed a more complete concept of consumer behavior such as Kardes et al (2011, p. 8), where consumer behavior is "all things. relating to consumer actions (decisions to buy, use and dispose of) and responses (consumer emotions, spirits, and behavior) to products and services they use in the past past or present”.

Thus, based on the above concept, it can be seen that consumer behavior research includes the following aspects:

The act of consumption: The connotation of the act of consumption includes the following aspects: the act of buying; use; and disposal of products and services. In which, buying activities are activities through which consumers get goods and services. Purchasing activities also include everything made that leads to a purchase, such as collecting and evaluating information about a product or service and choosing where to buy it, choosing a method of purchase and any translation. additional services such as installation, warranty ... use action is understood as all actions that take place in the process of consuming products and services of consumers. Disposal action refers to the actions of the customer when there is no longer a need to use certain products and services (removing, recycling, ceding the right to use ...)

Consumer feedback: is considered an important part of research on consumer decision making. Based on consumer feedback, marketers can predict how input influencing factors will affect the consumer decision-making process. Consumer feedback includes Emotional responses, Mental responses and behavioral responses. Emotions refer to the customer's feelings and moods. Mental responses include consumer thoughts, beliefs,

attitudes and intentions. Ultimately, behavioral responses are actions of choice decision-making and are the result of the process from information seeking, purchasing decisions to end consumption.

The concept of traveling decision used in the thesis is understood as consumer behavior of tourists with all the characteristics as mentioned above. Consumer decision processes (tourists) such as problem awareness, information retrieval, reviews, decisions, buying behavior ... are considered the nucleus of consumer behavior studies. in the tourism sector. However, the tourism product is considered to be highly synthetic, it is made up of many other services (transportation, accommodation, food, guide ...), therefore for decision travel is claimed by many scholars that it involves many sub-decisions. The decision to travel is greatly influenced by the decision-making context (Decrop, 2006b) and can be taken at many different levels, be it individuals, groups (other family members, members). group) or organizational decision.

Based on research by Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2010), the individual's role in tourism decision is divided according to the influence in the tourist's final decision as follows:

Initiator: is the family member or group that is the first to initiate a need or travel proposition.

Information gatherer: are individuals who have expertise and are interested in a particular tourism product. Different individuals may seek information at different times or on different aspects of a transaction.

Influencer: is the person who influences the choice of alternative travel products, the criteria for evaluating a travel product and influencing the final choice of a group of tourists.

Decision maker: is the individual who makes the final decision (these decisions can be individual decisions, but can also represent general decisions of the group).

Purchaser: is the person performing the payment action and specific purchase action.

User: is a participant who experiences a travel service product that has been previously decided to purchase.

The concept of Kardes et al (2011) is used as a theoretical basis for research development. The reason for this concept is supported and used as the basis for the next research steps because of its comprehensiveness and suitability when considering travel decisions as consumption actions. This concept is considered in many aspects: on the individual and collective sphere, the decision to travel is not merely about meeting the individual's needs and desires, but sometimes also. also in terms of satisfaction with other individuals (other family members, members in organizations, groups ...).

The characteristics of tourism products are invisible, the result after consumption is the remaining experiences in the perception of customers. Therefore, the travel decision-making process must be considered in a specific context and cannot be separated from the perceived and emotional factors of tourists before consuming products.

2.2 Theory of consumer behavior

In the 1950s of the last century, the first concepts of decision making were mentioned by Edwards (1954) in the field of psychology. These classical theories hold that people always collect and analyze information, ultimately choosing an optimal solution from a wide range of collected options. By assessing the advantages and disadvantages of each option, people choose the most appropriate one to achieve their wishes. Decision-making behavior is purely directed towards the subjective Expected Utility (SEU) of the individual decision-maker.

However, these theories have not yet shown the determinants of consumer behavior and decision-making. Kahneman and Tversky (1979) supplemented with the expectation theory (Prospect theory) and Loomes and Sugden (1982) with the Regret theory of assuming that consumers make good decisions in terms of risk and

zero. sure. This can be considered as the foundation for theoretical models explaining the decision-making process based on the reasonableness of the relationship between the impact factors in the later structured model.

The limitations of these theories manifest when reversing the research situation or the context of the action. These theories do not explain the causes of consumer behavior nor can it predict the outcome of choices according to previous input variables. Realizing the shortcomings of the pure model of SEU, Slovic et al. (1977); Einhorn and Hogarth (1981) reinforce the terms "risk" and "uncertainty" of decision. In addition, further development from the SEU model (Kahneman and Tversky, 2013) presents prospect theory and suggests that people rely more on benefits than losses when making their decisions. Loomes and Sugden (1982); Bell (1982) in his theory of avoiding regrets states that feelings of regret left over from past choices set the stage for individual decision-making behavior. However, these theories are still incomplete to describe the intermediate processes that lead to human decisions.

A further development in the research of consumer decision-making behavior since Simon (1955) has adopted a different approach to the decision-making approach by the theory of limited rationality (bounded rationality). Accordingly, he thinks that each individual when making a decision is aimed at optimizing profits or benefits, but due to cognitive limitations, limitations on the information they receive. Inadequate, this leads to a situation in which the decisions are not completely justified according to the original will of the decision maker. He also said that each individual's experience and behavioral history will influence that individual's satisfaction. The key point of this theory has approached in the direction of how the decision-making behavior process occurs, and thereby explains how the satisfaction of the individual decision-makers will influence their behavior.

Scholars have demonstrated that in each individual there is a difference in the formulation of evaluation criteria when making decisions. This means that the rules of choice are not the same for each individual (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979; Svenson, 1979). This approach assumes that decision making depends on personal characteristics (cognitive ability, available knowledge), the characteristics of the problem (task posing, context) and social context (responsibility). responsibility of individuals, group members) (Payne et al., 1993; Payne, 1982). Kahneman and Tversky (1979) have explained by paraphrase that a decisive side results from a balance between expectations and the reduction of losses. On the other hand, Puto (1987) argues that human decision is governed by the basic principle of perception or prediction of the benefit or damage in the outcome of that accompaniment.

The research on decision-making in the near modern time has made progress in asserting that the decision-making process is a combination of factors of complex nature. Depending on the context, each chosen condition, each solution and the outcome. The only thing that is common in all interpretive models of decision making is chronological (March, 1994).

Research on consumption decision-making currently is considered to have a particularly important role in researching consumer behavior. The summary of the above studies shows that in general, the theories of decision making mentioned in the development of consumer behavior studies can be divided into 2 groups:

The classical theories: approach decision-making behavior in three common ways: 1) Risk reduction is an individual's likelihood of having to predict the risks and consequences of buying goods (in uncertain conditions) when making a decision about what goods or services you will buy (Taylor, 1974). Risks can be physical benefits (price, product performance ...) or psychological (emotional, social relevance ...). This theory is based on the assumption that consumers are always looking for a solution that minimizes risk to the extent that they can afford it in consuming decisions. Decisions are made in terms of information limited to consumers. This is also the target of many classical economic studies towards such as loyalty to brands, repetitive consumer behavior, well-known brands or after-sales policies towards regular customers. 2) Problem solving is an approach based on the assumption that any individual who has a need or a desire to consume will have problems before making a consumption decision. Andreasen (1965) was the first to propose a consumer behavior model that emphasizes the importance of information processing in consumer decision-making. In

which consumer attitudes and sources of information are filtered and combined with other factors such as beliefs, rules, perceptions of substitute product value considered in terms of budget and suitability needs. Then the theory was developed through many scholars such as Howard and Sheth (1969); Engel et al (1973). The essence of this theory is that decision-making is that the individual seeks to solve the problems posed by consumption. Decision-making often involves steps from demand perception, information retrieval, evaluation of options, purchasing decisions, and post-purchase behavior (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975); 3) Information processing: Bettman et al. (1998) are based on the assumption that customers are always searching for and processing the information they obtain in order to improve the choices they make. Which is most evident in the limited rational choice theory. Besides, this research approach also thinks that the decision-making process is complex and people always build the optimal plan for each case when it is necessary to make a choice.

Near and modern theories: Nowadays, with the emergence of information technology, especially the popularity of the internet, it brings consumers a fuller and more diverse information from many sources. Consumers have more choices (brands, alternative products) when considering making decisions. Information sources are also more diverse such as family, friends, advertisers, salespeople, social reference groups ... (Decrop, 2006b). Consumers also place more demands on the products and services they intend to buy, and the market also offers more choices for consumers. Archaeological studies often refer to decision-making in terms of single choice (destination selection for tourists), while in the submodernist school of theory, there is a multi-choice approach. form and more comprehensive for products and services.

Studies to date on consumption decisions are generally divided into 5 groups of research approaches, including: Economics; psychology; behavioral science; cognitive science; and humanities.

The economic approach: The economics approach appeared very early, mainly based on theories of economics. Economic researchers believe that decision-making behavior is primarily based on maximizing the benefits consumers expect and minimizing the losses when making consumption decisions. Studies following this approach mostly assume that consumers will have to be aware of all available consumer options, be able to accurately evaluate each available option in order to choose the optimal one. most (Deaton and Muellbauer, 1980). In reality, however, consumers rarely have enough information, or enough time, to make a decision under such perfect conditions. Their decisions are often influenced by factors such as relationships and social values ... (Simon, 1947). Moreover, consumers tend to prioritize searching to satisfy their expectations rather than to seek the optimal option (Loomes and Sugden, 1982; Kahneman and Tversky, 2013). The economic approach theory is later supplemented with models to explain consumer decision-making purposes such as the rational choice theory. March (1994) proposes two main models: a rational choice decision-making model emphasizes the logic of consequences; and the model that explains the adequacy of decision-making (based on rules in particular circumstances). Lindblom (1959) asserts that people are not fixedly optimal or self-satisfied, but always seek to solve problems by searching for better solutions. This transition is considered at the level of expected achievement and is interpreted as the result of the continual desire to improve the choice better than the present situation.

Psychological approach: Consumer decision-making behavior is studied by psychologists as an instinctive act. In psychoanalysis theory, Arnold et al (2005) identified three interactive agents in the human psychological process, including: Self (Id), ego (ego) and super ego (SuperEgo) in which the being is the set of uncoordinated instinctual desires; the super ego plays a critical and moral role; and the ego is an organized reality agent, a mediator. These views suggest that behavior is influenced biologically through instinctive forces, or the forces of action outside of conscious thought. Foxall (1990) adds a view to behavioral research, arguing that the main principle of behavioral psychology is determined by the "drives", that is. What has been saved in the human brain, instead of individual perception, or environmental stimulation.

Behavioral science approach: Behavioral research theories claim that the nature of human behavior reflects the impact from the external environment to human actions, thoughts and feelings. The first is that Classical

Behaviorism theories such as Watson and Rayner (1920) study completely separate human behavior from mental life or inner attitudes. Subsequently, Skinner (1990) inherits the classical studies but adds to the evidence admitting the influence of inner emotions on the behavior of consumption. Jennings and Wattam (1998) contribute further by the theory of cognitive behavior (Cognitive Behaviorism) by suggesting that perception combined with facts about what is happening affects the behavior of the subject. Until now, behavioral research still contributes to our understanding of human behavior and is widely recognized in that it plays an important role in explaining the evolution of consumer behavior.

Approach to the humanistic science: Formed in the 1950s, scholars approach to explain customer behavior in a Humanistic Approach with a focus on self-affirmation of the decision-maker. Unlike other schools, the key point of this approach is that the consumer is the biggest actor and practices consumer behavior through belief in himself, instead of the main influence from other individuals or the external environment (Natarajan and Bagozzi, 1999). The gap between buying intent and buying decision is explained by human scientists by the concept of will. Bagozzi and Warshaw (1990) propose in Theory of Trying that consumers try to experiment with their attitudes toward expectations and attitudes with frustration to test their results. the results of the decisions I made. Perugini and Bagozzi (2001) inherit the previous theories and give the theory of the direct goal (Goal Directed Behavior) with the addition of a variable in causality to explain consumer behavior.

Approach to Cognitive Science: Contrary to the approach of behavioral science, the cognitive approach considers human to be an information processor. The subject of behavior is influenced by the impact of environmental factors and past consumer experiences. This influence occurs right from the process of finding and processing information within each individual when making a decision (Jennings and Wattam, 1998). These theories have roots in cognitive psychology, but it was not until the mid-20th century that cognitive theories really showed the importance of research contributions to decision-making behavior. Outstanding is the model SOR (Stimulus-Organism-Response), which includes stimulation, processing and feedback factors. This is the premise for a lot of later research. Cognitive models of consumer behavior according to a cognitive science approach include two types: analytical model and prescriptive statistical model.

2.3. The theory of tourism consumer behavior

Consumer products in tourist behavior studies can be viewed from many different perspectives. Decrop (2006b) and previous researchers have considered the tourism product to be both a social phenomenon and an economic product. Therefore, making decisions on tourism consumption not only receives a lot of attention from many researchers in the fields of psychology, sociology, anthropology or management science, but also broadens research. special in the field of economics.

Decision-making and the main variables of the travel decision are first of all considered from the perspective of a general decision (whether to go or not to travel). The decision to go or not to travel is made before a tourist makes sub-decisions (Van Raaij and Francken, 1984; Um and Crompton, 1990; Mansfeld, 1996). However, not all cases are subject to such order of decision making, in some cases tourists often make a sub-decision (choose destination, accommodation, supplier ...), after that is to decide whether to go or not (Decrop and Snelders, 2005). In addition, the decision variable is also considered based on the travel plan decision; the decision to pay for the purchase of travel products ...

The very early studies of Um and Crompton (1990) apply decision-making models in the selection of goods and services to the choice of tourist destination for vacation. Thereafter by Thornton et al (1997); Plog (2001); Litvin et al. (2004) extended with sub-decisions such as considerations of where to stay, how much money to spend on vacation, what activities to be involved ... in their research models. Researchers have also identified a number of ways to categorize decision-making when researching travel decision-making. Bronner and De Hoog (2008) have divided previous studies into three perspectives: personal choice, information seeking, and collective family decision-making. He also showed that previous studies can be described based on the decision-maker unit (individually or collectively) and information used by the decision-maker unit. Decrop and

Snelders (2005); Decrop (2006a); Decrop and Zidda (2006); Smallman and Moore (2010) believe that because of complexity, it is necessary to use approaches based on multiple directions simultaneously: epistemology, ontology ... etc when studying the variables affecting decision making. and learn how the decision-making process works. These scholars also propose that research should be placed in relation to the already complex environment of decision makers.

In general, the assumptions about consumer decision-making in tourism are largely derived from studies of general consumption. One can see prominent assumptions such as limited rationality (Simon, 1955) as the basis for a series of studies on utility maximization (Moutinho, 1987; Um and Crompton, 1990; Sirakaya and Woodside, 2005). Because the characteristics of tourism products are of the nature of social phenomena, containing in them the synthesis of many social activities. Therefore, theories that explain decision making and the decision-making process based on individual factors are not sufficient to explain complex social phenomena such as consumption of tourism products. Therefore, more research appears on these factors.

Theoretical model of consumption decision in tourism has been developed by many scholars, but can be divided into three main categories: Micro economic model; Cognitive models (including structured cognitive models and process perception); and paradigmatic framework model (Decrop, 2006b).

Model of decision making based on microeconomic factors appeared in the 70s of the last century. The basic theory is based on Lancaster's theory of consumption functions when approaching travel decision-making research based on the relationship between an individual's economic conditions and the expectation of satisfying the customer's needs . Customers will base on the budget limit to make the best choice of prices, transportation costs, trip length ... compared to the required rate for their trip.

Although attempting to explain the relationship between demand and cost, this model does not address the problems that are specific to tourism products (Decrop, 2006b). The main benefits brought about by tourism product consumption cannot be measured economically but by the emotions and feelings left behind after the trip (Rugg, 1973; Morley, 1992). Papatheodorou (2001) later added a number of elements to the model such as attraction and destination facilities, perceptions, perceptions and customer preferences (Papatheodorou, 2001; Seddighi and According to Charous, 2002), however, this supplement in a certain angle does not widely satisfy the explanation of consumer behavior of tourists.

The decision-making model based on customer perceptions differs from the economic model which focuses mainly on the relationship of economic benefit and the needs and expectations of the customer, the research of this model is based on The above variables belong to social psychology and decision-making process to explain customers' buying behavior. In these models, consumers' perception and information processing play a core role in the buying decision-making process. Thus can be divided into 2 types of cognitive models:

1) Structured decision-making model, based on the relationship between inputs (marketing variables, personal resources variables ...) and outputs (destination perception, plans to visit ...) provided that the information of each input factor is available. This is a common model and makes it easy for the empirical research to be carried out upon it. However, the limitation of this model is that the complexity of decision-making behavior is not fully explained as well as the correlation between the variables in the decision-making process (Crompton, 1979; Um and Crompton, 1990; Woodside and Lysonski, 1989).

2) The decision-making process model approaches the problem by explaining how the decision-making behavior occurs in the cognitive process. This model is quite commonly used to examine the key components of decision-making and connect them together (Mathieson and Wall, 1982; Van Raaij and Francken, 1984; Van Raaij, 1986; Moutinho, 1987; Goodall. , 1988). However, the limitation of this model is that it only proposed the model in a certain order and has not proven the hypotheses: whether the general decision (to participate or not to participate) was made first ; whether buying a travel is high-risk; Only the activity of collecting information can an individual tourist go to the tour selection stage or not.

The decision-making model is based on an interpretive framework on the premise that the stages in the decision-making process use an intrinsic and empirical perspective to approach the client's decision-making behavior. . In which, researchers propose a set of tools to select and apply an interpretive framework including variables and hypotheses that have never appeared in the traditional decision-making models before (Teare et al., 1994; Woodside and MacDonald, 1994; Hyde et al., 1999).

Studies on Vietnamese tourists' travel decisions for domestic tours have been mentioned in many recent studies. Side environmental factors include destination attractiveness, regional cultural differences, natural conditions such as forests, islands, or artificial recreational activities. However, most studies on factors that influence tourism decisions have chosen tourism destination as the central behavior of the decision.

Playing a core role in the decision of Vietnamese tourists when participating in a trip is choosing a destination. There are many theories about destination selection in the world tested in recent studies in Vietnam such as Nguyen Thi Quynh Anh (2016); Ho Bach Nhat and Nguyen Phuong Khanh (2018); Nguyen Xuan Hiep (2016). The main factors classified according to external influences include destination image; information from social networks and media (Nguyen Xuan Hiep, 2016). Internal factors such as cultural, economic, and demographic characteristics. The influence tourists perceive through attitudes toward destination image, and thus influence the choice of destination in their travel itinerary. Nguyen Thi Quynh Anh (2016) said that perceptions of tourism risks and experiences have a positive impact on the choice of tourist destinations, research from the case of tourists to Ly Son Island. In recent research, Ho Bach Nhat and Nguyen Phuong Khanh (2018) have quite clearly divided the aspects that make up the image of the point that dominates the tourist's decision to choose, including: infrastructure; cultural history; entertainment and relaxation; political-economic; food, shopping; and landscape environment.

In the study of behavioral intentions of tourists, particularly Nha Trang tourism, Vo Hoan Hai (2010) said that satisfaction (the factor inherited from the basic theoretical model of behavioral planning TPB) is dominated by product quality factors along with factors of social norms, behavioral control that positively affects the intention of the visitor to perform behavior. At the same time, it is the intent to perform the behavior that not only plays an important role in the behavioral decision-making process, but it also affects the frequency of the behavior - which is inherited from the satisfaction model and frequency. the behavior of Olsen (2002). Factors affecting intention (choosing destination, returning) are also mentioned in studies placed in the context of recent Vietnamese tourist behavior such as Bui Anh Tuan et al (2018); Canh Chi Hoang and Tran Ngoc Tu (2018); Le Thi Kim Tuyet and Ngo Thi Sa Ly (2017); Tran Phan Doan Khanh and Nguyen Le Thuy Lien (2020); Pham Thi Ngoc Tram and Le Phong Lam (2016).

Factors belonging to corporate performance are studied by several researchers recently. In which, the authors Canh Chi Hoang and Tran Ngoc Tu (2018) affirmed that the price factor and accessibility to customers are two of the important factors that have a positive impact on the intention of tourists to return. guest. In other words, there is an impact from these factors on the customer's internal feelings that lead to their choice decisions. In addition, according to Ta Thi Thanh Huong and Nguyen Thi Bich Thuy (2016), the design characteristics of tourism products, service attitude and professionalism of the staff are also key factors in the image. directly enjoy the decision for a tourist's trip. Ngo Cao Hoai Linh and Le Chi Cuong (2017) said that market orientation factors (MO-Market Orientation) have an impact on tourism behavior. In which, market orientation has a connotation of the activities of the business, including: customer orientation; competitive orientation; functional coordination; and respond quickly. Market-oriented activities, through an intermediate variable being perceived value, have a positive impact on tourist behavior. In other words, the impact of customer outreach activities on tourist decisions is confirmed by empirical evidence from this study. In addition, the study of Ngo My Tran et al (2016) provides additional evidence on the cost factor impacting tourism demand. Costs here include: the cost of the destination; living expenses at tourist sites; and the cost of the substitute goods.

Not only choosing a destination but more generally deciding to join the tour, Ta Thi Thanh Huong and Nguyen Thi Bich Thuy (2016). Factors that directly affect the decision to choose a trip to a tourist destination include tourism product factors; price; location of the destination; the media; Staff; procedure; and customer service. As can be seen, the decision to join the tour is not only based on the decision to choose the destination, but the factors of the products and activities of the business also influence the decision of the customer.

Hoang Thanh Nhon and Nguyen Kim Thu (2014) argue that the two most important factors that directly affect customers' travel decisions are positive product expectations and perceptions of the trustworthiness of information sources. believe. These factors are governed by attributes of information in the online environment such as similarity, identity of information source, openness and internet expertise of users. In particular, the perception of the reliability of information has a stronger impact on the customers' travel decisions.

Travel demand and motivation is one of the most mentioned factors in recent studies about the intention to choose or intend to return of tourists. Le Thi Kim Tuyet and Ngo Thi Sa Ly (2017) argue that tourism motivation has a direct impact on the intention to return to tourism consumption and indirectly affects tourism behavior through visitor satisfaction. . In the study of Ngo Cao Hoai Linh et al (2017), tourism motivation is shown by tourism demand. In which the factors that have the greatest influence on tourism demand include: self-expressing demand; Exploration; personal links; social links; escapism; and excitement. These factors contribute to the tourism demand that drives consumers to the travel products they want. In another angle, Pham Thi Mong Hang (2020) shows that factors of personal control resources such as marital status, age, income ... play an important role in influencing demand. tourism of tourists.

Tourists' attitudes towards tourism products or tourist destinations are mentioned in the study by Huynh Nhut Phuong and Nguyen Thuy An (2017). In particular, the intention to perform acts (decision to join the travel program) of tourists is influenced by attitude factors. The attitude factor here is the customer's feelings and feelings about the destination. This study examines one aspect of the relationship between the destination image and the travel experience and visitor attitudes, as part of Ajzen's TPB planning behavior theory (1991). In the context of the study is the behavior of Vietnamese tourists to Can Tho, our research has shown a proportional relationship between attitudes and physical factors at the destination. Tourists' attitudes were affected by price and safety and security at the tourist destination. Negative guest perceptions of service price increases and theft, enticing tourists in a tourist destination.

The characteristics of tourists consumed in the selection and decision of tours are outlined in studies. In particular, the tourist destination is one of the most important factors affecting the choice of Vietnamese tourists to domestic destinations. Typical examples are the studies of Nguyen Thi Quynh Anh (2016); Pham Hong Hai (2019); Than Trong Thuy (2018); Nguyen Xuan Hiep (2016); Ho Minh Thu et al (2018).

Most recent studies have mentioned the influence of technological factors on the decisions of domestic tourists. The latest research must include Bui Anh Tuan et al (2017a); Trinh Thi Thu and Bui Duc Hung (2017); Bui Anh Tuan et al (2017b). Empirical evidence in research by Bui Anh Tuan et al (2017b) helps confirm that the quality and reliability of information are important factors affecting the choice of destination for Vietnamese tourists. . Attributes of disseminated information include: Quality of information; Necessity of information; and Attitude towards information receptive. In which, the attitude factor with received information has the greatest influence on the intention to choose a tourist destination. In fact, online communication platforms such as discussion forums, review websites, social networking sites ... etc, have gradually become the most popular channels for exchanging information about visitors. Vietnamese calendar (Bui Anh Tuan et al., 2017a). In addition, the industrial revolution 4.0 has created new consumer trends in the tourism sector. One of the trends is information tourism, including aspects: intelligent needs and intelligent management techniques; and smart marketing (Trinh Thi Thu and Bui Duc Hung, 2017).

Another study by Ngo Dinh Tam (2019) shows that not only word of mouth, but also the transmission of images via electronic word of mouth (eWOM) also has an impact on the customers' choice of destination. travel.

Accordingly, the factor of eWOM acceptance (influenced by the quality of eWOM and the credibility of the eWOM) has an impact on the destination image and at the same time, the intention of tourists to choose a destination. And therefore, indirectly influence their decision to choose a travel destination. Another study by Huynh Van Thai et al (2019) adds a relationship that reflects the impact between the destination image (mentioned aspects such as natural characteristics; infrastructure; atmosphere travel; travel comfort; and affordable) with satisfaction and electronic word of mouth. This research report shows the positive impact of destination image on tourist satisfaction. Tac is the attitude towards a tourist destination that brings sympathy to tourists or not depends on the destination image very much. At the same time, it is that satisfied attitude that motivates tourists through electronic word of mouth to spread information to other guests.

Nowadays, with the explosion of information technology and global telecommunications, information search is seen as the early stage of decision-making, where tourists act as information seekers. Useful for their travel needs, but at the same time they serve as informants through sharing their own experiences with others. Research by Luu Tien Thuan (2017) shows the impact of search intent on tourism information retrieval behavior. There are 6 groups of factors that have a positive influence on visitor's intention to seek information: accessibility; usefulness; subjective standards; trust; personal experience; and behavior control awareness. In which, the factor that has the strongest impact on tourism information seeking behavior is awareness of controlling visitor behavior.

Although the studies presented above have initially shown the factor influencing the decision-making relationship of Vietnamese tourists. However, there are quite big differences when applying research to factors affecting the Vietnamese people's decision to go abroad. Specifically, that difference is first and foremost in different research contexts. While the above studies are located in the context of research is the act of deciding to choose a domestic destination, or to choose a specific tourism product to a specific locality in Vietnam. Therefore, there is no difference in the language of travelers compared to their chosen destination. In addition, the differences in cultural and social environments only reflect the differences between localities in the country, not between cultures between countries. Therefore, when applying the decision-making behavior study of overseas Vietnamese tourists, the theoretical models and research results used in the above-mentioned studies may not be appropriate. Due to the differences in language, cultural and social environment between the living environment of the visitors (Vietnam) and the countries in their travel itinerary.

The studies mentioned above have analyzed, measured and tested the relationship between the basic factors affecting tourism decisions of Vietnamese people such as destination image, tourism motivation, information sources. information about references, attitudes and perceptions about tourism products ... etc. However, there are no studies showing the comprehensiveness or applying the general model to simultaneously test these relationships to tourist behavior. In fact, previous studies around the world showed that the decision to travel is a complex behavior, governed by many of the above factors. So to see the different levels of influence on tourist's behavior.

Although there have been some studies applying Ajzen's planned behavioral theory (1991) to explain decision-making behavior of Vietnamese tourists such as Pham Thi Ngoc Tram and Le Phong Lam (2016) ; Le Chi Cong (2017); Luu Tien Thuan (2017); Ngo Dinh Tam (2019); Pham Hong Hai (2019). However, these studies just stop at partly explaining the relationship between factors affecting behavior (decision to join a tour) or applied in the context of research is behavior. selection of domestic destinations in Vietnam. Applying to the behavioral research context of Vietnamese traveling abroad requires testing of the hypotheses and a more comprehensive approach to explain the causes and the mechanism of impact of the factors. to the tourist's behavior.

3. Research Methods

The research methods used in the thesis are a combination of qualitative research methods and quantitative research methods. The reason for the combination of the two research methods is because of the specific characteristics of the research context and characteristics of the consumption culture of Vietnamese tourists.

The study is in the socio-cultural and tourism market context of the Vietnamese people, so there is no similarity with the context in previous studies in Western countries. Therefore, it is necessary to use qualitative research methods to analyze the initial discovery, evaluate the suitability of the model, and adjust the scale of variables in quantitative research for the research context in Vietnam. . Qualitative research was carried out by in-depth interviews with 10 tourism experts and sample in-depth interviews with 15 Vietnamese tourists.

From there, proposing experimental research model.

4. Results

The research review shows that the nature of influences from individual psychological factors, environmental factors on tourist consumption behavior is not fixed. It depends on the characteristics of the culture of consumption, which changes over time. The tourism product is not only viewed from the perspective of a purely service product, but it is also seen as a "socio-economic" phenomenon (Decrop, 2006b, p.14). Thus, in order to see the substantial relationship of the factors affecting the consumer behavior of tourists, it is necessary to place the factors in the overall binding relationship. From an overview of previous studies on customer behavior and decision-making of travelers, the author found that there are gaps in the theory that need more to deepen understanding of behavior. The tourist's decision-making is as follows:

First: Although there are many studies in the world about travel decisions, most of these studies have been done in the context of research that are countries with Western cultures or the Northeast. Asia, where there are great cultural and social differences compared to Vietnam. As most scholars, in particular Blackwell et al (2001, p.314) have affirmed that in different socio-cultural contexts, the factors that influence tourists' decisions are different. Tourism consumption culture in Vietnam has its own characteristics, not only influenced by culture, but also influenced by other environmental factors such as economy, policy mechanisms ... etc. However, to date, there are not many studies on the topic that influences the factors that affect the decision to travel abroad in Southeast Asia, and particularly rarely research on this topic in the context of. Foreign tourism market in Vietnam. Theoretical gaps such as determining which factors, how they affect the overseas tourism decisions of Vietnamese people are not clear.

Second: Recent domestic research on tourism decision mainly focuses on Vietnamese domestic travel decision. However, overseas travel is quite different from domestic travel. This difference firstly sees the difference in the tourist environment (natural landscape, culture, social institution ...) in the destination countries; the attraction of foreign tourist destinations; differences in tourism product design; procedural barriers, language ... etc. Therefore, the theoretical models and research results from domestic studies cannot be satisfied when applied in the context of Vietnamese tourism abroad. Through the overview, there are currently no comprehensive studies on the Vietnamese decision to travel abroad. From practical research to fill the gap in knowledge about travel decisions to be able to explain the current trend of overseas tourism in Vietnam.

Third: The proliferation of the internet and the global information network changes the role of factors influencing travel decisions. Research by Kotler et al (2016) has shown that in the 4.0 era, the rapid change gives rise to new factors. Among these new factors, the most important factor influencing a travel decision is social networks. These new factors can enhance or weaken the degree to which other factors influence a tourist's tourism decision. Research by Qing et al. (2012) showed that electronic word of mouth (eWOM) had a significant impact on customer decision-making. The impact from the perception of a tourist destination, searching for information, evaluating tourism products, to changing the consumption habits of tourists. It therefore affects all factors, at all stages of the consumer decision-making process. From that fact, the theoretical models require an update in response to the interpretation of this change. However, in the context of overseas Vietnamese tourism, almost no research has been able to meet the actual requirements of this change. These research models only focus on theoretical perspectives on one (or several) individual factors influencing the decisions of foreign tourists in Vietnam. Reality requires a research model that comprehensively reflects the relationship between individual psychological factors (attitude, motivation); How environmental factors

(destination image, customer outreach activities, reference group) put in the overall impact on the decision to travel abroad.

With the above theoretical gaps, studying the factors and their impact on the decision to travel abroad of Vietnamese people will partly fill and deepen understanding of the practice. micro-consumer consumption, in this case Vietnamese tourists.

Research models

To point out the factors influencing the decision of Vietnamese to travel abroad and the relationship between these factors, the author inherits the theories that explain Ajzen's planned behavior (1991). and explanatory theories of factors influencing tourist behavior including Um and Crompton (1990); Woodside and MacDonald (1994); Decrop (2006b). Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) was developed from Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). Derived from the cognitive approach, planned behavioral theory shows the relationship between stimuli to attitudes, motives, intentions and consumer decision-making behaviors. mentioned earlier by the author (Ajzen, 1985). The limitation of Reasonable Action Theory states that human behavior is controlled by reason. By adding the new factor, Behavioral Control Awareness, (Ajzen, 1991) added the irrational factor to increase the accuracy of human behavior prediction model.

The main elements in the planned behavioral theory model include Attitude toward the Behavior; Subjective Norms; and Perceived Behavioral Control. In which, Attitude is a psychological factor in each individual, reflecting the set of emotions and has a great impact on intentions to perform acts. Attitude is the result of influences from environmental stimuli such as product characteristics, or results from marketing activities. The subjective benchmark factor is individual perception affected by social normative pressure. This awareness is influenced by the judgment that the individual should or should not perform the act. The people who are important to influencing subjective standards include family and social groups. The Cognitive element of behavior control is an individual's perception of an ability to perform a particular behavior. It affects the intention to perform the behavior, but it also directly affects the tendency to perform the behavior if the individual is correctly aware of his level of control.

The Behavioral Intent factor in the multidimensional conceptual model refers to human behavior that can predict that behavior will happen in the future or will inevitably happen. Intent denotes human willingness to try something. In the models developed from planned behavioral theory, Intent is the factor that motivates and influences specific behavior. The Traveler Intent variable is measured by: Positive speech; intention to buy back; and price sensitivity. Blackwell et al. (2001) define that intention is a probability that an act translates into an act, or a probability that subjective ability translates into a particular act. Previous studies have confirmed not only the quality of a tour but past experiences and experiences that help shape customers' intention to join tours. In addition, the perception of the security of the destination, the perception of the destination image of the tourists are also influencing the intention of customers to choose tourism products (Beirne and Curry, 1999; Baker and Crompton, 2000; Petrick et al., 2001; Chen and Tsai, 2007).

Also developed based on the Reasonable Action Theory model, the model of Um and Crompton (1990) concretized and added factors from the external environment when explaining the destination selection behavior of tourists. calendar. The core factors influencing behavior are initially classified into factors from the external environment and the psychological factors that affect the perception towards human behavior. The destination image factor is mentioned as an important and central factor of this model.

5. Conclusion

The importance of research on decision-making behavior and the factors that influence the decision-making process is a topic of primary concern for researchers. Along with the growth of the tourism industry in recent years, there has been a change in the research landscape. Contributing significantly to the change is the

development of information technology and the popularity of social networking platforms. In that context, assessing the impact of these factors on tourist's consumer behavior plays an important role in marketing research, helping to access and expand the market of businesses. more advantageous. From both theoretical and practical perspectives, the application of theoretical models and practical studies in the Vietnamese tourism market context is of great significance to travel businesses.

Research results on the current situation of overseas tourism in Vietnam show that economic conditions and internationalized environment have boosted the growth of overseas tourism for Vietnamese people over the past decade. The trend of rapid growth in both the number of tourists and the range of tourist destinations is expanding. The number of Vietnamese tourists going abroad in 2016 reached 4.8 million with a growth of 9.5% per year (Choong and Wong, 2017) showing the growth of the overseas tourism market in Vietnam. Men are in the leading group in Asia (second only after Myanmar). The growth chart in the typical overseas tourism markets shows the trend that has continuously increased over the years. The fact that the supply source of the foreign tourism market in Vietnam also grew during the period 2010 to 2019. With the research results of the current real situation in Vietnam, the thesis provides an overview. on market supply and demand, socio-economic context and international integration. From the context of change the factors affecting the decision to travel abroad come from the change in science and technology.

The general information about the foreign tourism market in this research is the premise for studying foreign tourism issues in Vietnam. The information base on foreign tourism not only shows problems in terms of economy, market trends, consumer habits ... but also shows social problems, consider foreign tourism as an inevitable phenomenon and trend of modern society in the international integration environment. Questions raised from the current overseas tourism context of Vietnam such as: What is the main cause of the current growth of overseas tourism in Vietnam? What is the trend of choosing foreign tourism products of Vietnamese people?

General theoretical model of factors affecting the decision to travel abroad is established on the theoretical basis and overview of previous studies. In which, the model reflects the relationship between the representative factors of the group of factors from the external environment (destination image, customer outreach activities, reference group) that have an impact on psychological factors. within each individual (attitudes towards foreign travel, travel motivation) and thereby influence the decision of Vietnamese to travel abroad. Inheriting from the research model of Ajzen (1991); Um and Crompton (1990); Woodside and MacDonald (1994); Decrop (2006b), the author proposed a model suitable for the research context.

An overview of recent studies also shows that the emergence of new factors has a significant influence on customers' decisions to choose foreign travel destinations. In the context of the explosion of the global internet, information about the Destination Image is conveyed to tourists more fully (including information, photos, sharing experiences of others). This is a big difference in the studies before and after the 2000s of the last century, a time that marks the presence of the internet and the popularization of social networks. Therefore, the attractiveness of the information about the destination image to the attitude and travel motivation of customers also changes compared to the conclusions from many previous studies.

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